

THE NUTRITIONAL VALUE OF CAULIFLOWER AND ITS MAIN BENEFITS

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cauliflower, producing leaves, florets, cabbage, growing, transplanted, ripens, cultivate, bunch, nutritional value, Health benefits of cauliflower, blood pressure, risk of cancer, losing weight, carbohydrate.

цветная капуста, образующая листья, соцветия, капуста, выращивание, пересадка, созревание, выращивание, гроздь, пищевая ценность, польза цветной капусты для здоровья, кровяное давление, риск рака, похудение, углеводы.

The cauliflower is an annual plant, vegetable crop belonging to the cauliflower-cabbage family. After producing 15-20 leaves, it forms a head (300-500 g) in the upper part of the stem. The head consists of many short florets, and its shape (large and small, degree of growth) depends on the type of cauliflower and growing conditions. After the head of cabbage is formed, some of the stems continue to grow, turning into inflorescences, flowers and seeds. The flower is white or yellow. Cauliflower is biologically similar to ordinary cabbage, but it cooks faster. After the seedling is transplanted, the head of cabbage ripens in 50-60 days. It contains 7-3.3% dry matter, 1.2-4.4% sugar, 1.5-3.7% protein, 0.7-0.8% mineral substances. Vitamin C and A, potassium, iron, phosphorus salts are more than in ordinary cabbage. It is dipped in the mentioned egg and fried, the soup is a delicious and diet food, canned food is prepared. Cauliflower is resistant to cold (-3-5°), its seedlings are planted in spring (March) and summer (July) in a scheme of 60x30, 70x35 cm. The spring one ripens in May-June, the summer one in October-November. For quality ripening, the leaves are tied in bunches on the head or the head is shaded with broken leaves. It is cultivated in all regions of Uzbekistan.

Cauliflower's delicious taste and excellent nutritional value have made it a truly desirable product, and major food companies and restaurants around the world have paid special attention to it. Cauliflower is among the many foods that are loved, it eases

the digestion process through carbohydrates. In this article, we will present to you the unknown features of this product. The nutritional value of cauliflower is as follows:

calories: 25 kcal;
sodium: 30 mg;
carbohydrates: 5 grams;
fiber: 2 grams;
sugar: 2 grams;
Vitamin C: 100 percent;
potassium: 8 percent;
calcium: 2 percent;
iron: 2 percent.

Cauliflower is rich in vitamins and minerals: vitamin B5 - 13.3%, vitamin B9 - 14.3%, vitamin C - 53.6%, vitamin K - 12.9%, potassium - 12%

- Vitamin B5 participates in protein, fat, carbohydrate metabolism, cholesterol metabolism, a number of hormones, hemoglobin synthesis, ensures the absorption of amino acids and sugar in the intestines, supports the work of the adrenal cortex. Lack of pantothenic acid can cause damage to the skin and mucous membranes.

- As vitamin B6 coenzymes, they participate in the metabolism of nucleic acids and amino acids. Folate deficiency leads to disruption of nucleic acids and protein synthesis, resulting in inhibition of cell growth and division, especially in rapidly proliferating tissues: bone marrow, intestinal epithelium, etc. Inadequate intake of folate during pregnancy is one of the causes of premature birth, malnutrition, birth defects and developmental disorders of the child. There is a strong correlation between folate and homocysteine levels and the risk of cardiovascular disease.

- vitamin C participates in oxidation-reduction reactions, the functioning of the immune system, stimulates the absorption of iron. Deficiency causes loose and bleeding gums and nosebleeds due to increased permeability and fragility of blood vessels.

- vitamin K regulates blood clotting. Lack of vitamin K leads to an increase in blood clotting time, a decrease in the amount of prothrombin in the blood.

- forms potassium, which is the main intracellular ion involved in the control of water, acid and electrolyte balance, nerve impulses, pressure regulation.

- Health benefits of cauliflower

Despite its plain white color, cauliflower is rich in vitamins and contains various phytochemicals and antioxidants. This nutrient provides health benefits including:
Reduces the risk of inflammation

Antioxidants in cauliflower help protect cells from damage and oxidative stress that lead to chronic diseases. Also, one of the conducted studies proved an inverse relationship between the consumption of vegetables such as cauliflower and the risk of developing a number of chronic diseases.

- Reduces the risk of cancer

While neither product has been linked to tumor prevention or growth, cauliflower contains a compound called sulforaphane that may help stop abnormal cell growth. However, eating large amounts of these vegetables can reduce the risk of all kinds of chronic diseases.

- Helps regulate blood pressure

One study found that sulforaphane, a compound found in cauliflower, was also associated with lower blood pressure. In addition, studies have shown that cruciferous vegetables play a major role in preventing heart disease.

- Protects the bone

Cauliflower is rich in vitamin K, which is essential for bone mineral density and blood clotting.

- Increases immunity

One serving of cauliflower contains 100 percent of the daily value of vitamin C, which helps support the immune system and plays a special role in repairing DNA in the body. Vitamin C protects against infection and even stimulates the formation of antibodies to fight diseases.

- Does cauliflower help you lose weight?

Cauliflower is a great choice for those trying to lose weight, given its low calorie content. By choosing cauliflower, you can significantly reduce your calorie and carbohydrate intake, while it also contains extra fiber to help keep you full. In addition, more than 90 percent of cauliflower consists of water.

Conclusion: Cauliflower, like all vegetables, is a carbohydrate. However, it is a complex non-starchy variety that is high in fiber and low in sugar. Cauliflower contains one-sixth the carbohydrates of a bowl of cooked pasta or rice, making it a great choice for diabetics or those watching their blood sugar. Highly processed carbohydrates like

white bread, white rice, and white pasta contain fewer nutrients than other alternatives. But cauliflower's nutrients have antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.

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